

A Comparison of Clinico-Functional Outcome and Efficacy of Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) and Local Corticosteroid Injection in the Treatment of Tennis Elbow (Lateral Epicondylar Tendinosis)

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Abstract

Lateral epicondylitis, sometimes known as Tennis elbow, is a frequently reported musculoskeletal condition affecting the upper extremity. Lateral epicondylitis is caused by repetitive action that results in tension on the extensor tendons. As a result, this leads to discomfort and tendinosis at the point where the tendon attaches to the lateral epicondyle. The majority of instances of Lateral epicondylitis are managed conservatively with a range of procedures, including injections. This study aimed to compare the functional outcome and efficacy of Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) with Local Corticosteroid Injection in the treatment of Tennis Elbow. This is a prospective randomized controlled trial. 40 patients were recruited and they were randomized into 2 groups. Group A received PRP injection and group B received corticosteroid injection. Patients progress was assessed by pain VAS, Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS), and Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH) before treatment, at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months after treatment. The mean (SD) age of the patients was 40.6 (8.68) in PRP group and 41.4 (10.04) in corticosteroid group. There were 11 (55%) females and 9 (45%) males in PRP group and 14 (70%) females and 6 (30%) males in corticosteroid group. The pain VAS, MEPS and DASH score were significantly better in 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months and 6 months after treatment ($p < 0.0001$) in both PRP and corticosteroid groups. All parameters were better in corticosteroid group in 2 weeks and better in PRP group in 6 weeks. Study concludes that Tennis Elbow (Lateral Epicondylar Tendinosis) treated with Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) is more efficient than those treated with Local Corticosteroid Injection at the end of 6 months.

Keywords: Lateral epicondylitis, Tennis elbow, Corticosteroid, Platelet-rich plasma.

Introduction

Tennis Elbow, sometimes referred to as Lateral Epicondylitis and Lateral Epicondylalgia, is a prevalent source of elbow discomfort among adults, impacting approximately 1-2% of the overall population annually. The prevalence is significantly greater in some demographics, such as those who play tennis (9–40%) as well as people engaged in strenuous labor. It results in discomfort and hinders the ability to do daily tasks effectively [1].

The histological results in chronic instances indicate that tendinosis is not a disorder characterized by acute inflammation. Instead, it is a result of the normal tendon healing process failing, which is coupled with angiofibroblastic degeneration [2].

Recent research has generated multiple biological hypotheses about the root cause of tendinosis. These theories are founded on histopathological, biochemical processes, as well as clinical observations that indicate cell death, angiofibroblastic characteristics, or abnormal biochemical adaptations [3]. Overall, these findings strongly suggest that the condition is primarily caused by a deficient healing reaction. The extensor carpi radialis brevis is the muscle most frequently affected, although additional muscles including the supinator, extensor carpi radialis longus, extensor digitorum, extensor digiti minimi, as well as extensor carpi ulnaris can also be involved. The extensor carpi radialis brevis is very prone to tissue degeneration caused by lateral epicondylitis due to the lack of blood supply to the undersurface. Lateral epicondylitis earned the moniker "Tennis Elbow" as a result of the repetitive arm motions required in tennis, namely involving the extensor and supinator muscles [4].

Lateral Epicondylitis is often a self-limiting illness that will spontaneously cure in about 90% of cases before one year without the need for surgical intervention. Nevertheless, a prior investigation revealed that 27% of individuals diagnosed with Lateral Epicondylitis experienced significant challenges in performing their daily activities [5]. Additionally, 5% of those diagnosed with lateral epicondylitis had to take time off from work because of their elbow complaints, averaging 29 sick days within the past year. Therefore, it is necessary to develop remedies for lateral epicondylitis that can promptly alleviate patients' discomfort. Multiple therapy modalities are available for this prevalent ailment. The initial approach to treatment is conservative [6].

Various treatment options have been recommended for tennis elbow, such as rest, anti-inflammatory drugs, bracing, physical therapy, iontophoresis, extracorporeal shockwave therapy, and botulinum toxin. In refractory situations, treatments such as corticosteroid injections, dry needling, and other surgical methods might be utilized [7]. Nevertheless, these conventional treatments do not modify the tendon's inadequate healing qualities caused by insufficient blood supply. Due to the inherent characteristics of the tendon, novel treatment approaches such as Platelets Rich Plasma (PRP), autologous blood, prolotherapy, as well as extracorporeal shock wave treatment are designed to stimulate inflammation versus inhibit it. Corticosteroid injections are considered the most effective treatment, but, their impact is just temporary, lasting for a period of 2 to 6 weeks [8].

Autologous Platelet Rich Plasma is believed to aid in healing by triggering an inflammatory response and supplying nutrients and concentrated growth factors that can potentially enhance tendon recovery [9]. This study aimed to compare the functional outcome and efficacy of Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) with Local Corticosteroid Injection in the treatment of Tennis Elbow.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants

This is a prospective randomized controlled trial done in the department of Orthopaedics in an academic tertiary care private institution from November 2023 to September 2024. Study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee. (Ref. no:1136/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023; IEC No: 153, Dated: 26.10.2023). All patients 18 to 60 years of age, diagnosed with tennis elbow and resistant to conservative therapy for more than 6 months were included in the study. Patients who had received any previous treatment in the form of local injections of steroid, patients with bony lesions at elbow (assessed by X-ray of elbow), patients with systemic diseases (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, rheumatoid arthritis), carpal tunnel syndrome or cervical radiculopathy were excluded from the study.

Recruitment

40 patients who attended the Orthopaedic OPD diagnosed with tennis elbow clinically and radiologically and consented for the study were screened and eligible patients were

recruited. They were randomized to 2 groups A and B based on computer generated random numbers. Patient and the investigator were blinded to which arm they belong to.

Intervention

Group A (Autologous PRP)

The treatment approach for individuals in this group involved administering a single injection with 2 ml of autologous PRP at the origin of the wrist extensors, specifically targeting the area of maximum discomfort in the elbow region. The injection was performed using aseptic technique.

To prepare 2 ml of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) with a concentration 4-6 times higher than the typical normal values, a total of 20 ml of blood was initially taken from the patient's cubital vein utilising an 18 G needle. Next, 2 milliliters of ACD-A (Anticoagulant Citrate Dextrose Solution, Solution A) introduced into the sample as an anticoagulant. A single milliliter of a peripheral blood sample was provided for a comprehensive blood count. The remaining sample successfully underwent two phases of centrifugation. The first stage involved spinning at a speed of 1600 RPM lasting 15 minutes to separate the Red Blood Cells. The second step involved spinning at a speed of 2800 RPM for 7 minutes to concentrate the platelets. The end result consisted of 2 milliliters of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) that contained leukocytes, also known as leukocyte-rich PRP.

The patient is positioned in a suitable and comfortable manner that ensures sterility and provides easy access to the injection site. The area to be injected was prepared and covered with a sterile drape, and then the clear PRP was administered using a sterile 18 G needle (Figure 4). The patient underwent a PRP injection at the most optimal location on the elbow utilizing a procedure that involves spreading the injection in a circular pattern to cover a larger area.

Group B (Corticosteroid)

Group B had a 2ml (80 mg) administration with Methylprednisolone without any local anaesthetic administration (Figure 5). This was done to prevent any disruption in the study findings.

Outcomes and Measures

The patient's progress was assessed using the Visual Analog Score (VAS), Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS), and Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH) before treatment, at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months after treatment.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was carried out using the statistical package IBM-SPSS 26.0. For each patient composite score was based on Visual Analog Score (VAS), Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS), Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH). Based on the composite scores of all scoring systems, mean value with Standard Deviation was computed during the time period of pre-treatment and 6 months post-treatment. Change in the mean values from pre-treatment to post-treatment were computed using Student T Paired test, further percentage was computed based on Composite scores at the end of 6 months, which is divided into categories of improved and non-improved. Further odds ratio with 95% confidence interval was calculated to identify the best procedure. $P < 0.005$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic characteristics

The mean (SD) age of the patients was 40.6 (8.68) in PRP group and 41.4 (10.04) in corticosteroid group. There were 11 (55%) females and 9 (45%) males in PRP group and 14 (70%) females and 6 (30%) males in corticosteroid group.

Visual Analog Score (VAS)

The pain VAS was significantly lower in 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months and 6 months after treatment ($p < 0.0001$) in both PRP and corticosteroid groups. Pain VAS was better in corticosteroid group in 2 weeks and better in PRP group in 6 weeks. Mean pain VAS and comparison of both groups are given in Table 1, Table 4 and Figure 1.

Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS)

The Mayo Elbow Performance Score was significantly better in 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months and 6 months after treatment ($p < 0.0001$) in both PRP and corticosteroid groups.

MEPS was better in corticosteroid group in 2 weeks and better in PRP group in 6 weeks. Mean Mayo Elbow Performance Score and comparison of both groups are given in Table 2, Table 4 and Figure 2.

Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH)

The Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale was significantly better in 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months and 6 months after treatment ($p < 0.0001$) in both PRP and corticosteroid groups. DASH was better in corticosteroid group in 2 weeks and better in PRP group in 6 weeks. Mean Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale and comparison of both groups are given in Table 3, Table 4 and Figure 3.

Table 1: Pain VAS in both groups (n=40)

PRP/ CS	Treatment	Mean	SD	95% CI		P Value
				Lower bound ($\alpha=2.5\%$)	Upper bound ($\alpha=97.5\%$)	
PRP	Before treatment	8.30	1.42	7.68	8.92	
	2 weeks	7.2	1.2	5.13	6.17	<0.0001
	6 weeks	4.20	1.28	3.64	4.76	<0.0001
	3 months	3.15	1.42	2.53	3.77	<0.0001
	6 months	1.65	0.49	1.76	2.74	<0.0001
CS	Before treatment	7.90	1.48	7.25	15.15	
	2 weeks	6.05	1.05	5.59	11.64	<0.0001
	6 weeks	5.25	1.21	4.72	9.97	<0.0001
	3 months	3.60	1.60	2.90	6.50	<0.0001
	6 months	2.25	1.16	1.74	3.99	<0.0001

Table 2: Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS) in both groups (n=40)

PRP/ CS	Treatment	Mean	SD	95% CI		P Value
				Lower bound ($\alpha=2.5\%$)	Upper bound ($\alpha=97.5\%$)	
PRP	Before treatment	51.25	12.76	45.66	56.84	
	2 weeks	61.5	11.37	69.21	77.29	0.04
	6 weeks	81.50	8.90	77.60	85.40	<0.0001
	3 months	78.00	6.57	75.12	80.88	<0.0001
	6 months	90.5	4.56	82.63	88.87	<0.0001
CS	Before treatment	55.25	11.18	50.35	105.60	
	2 weeks	72.50	9.10	68.51	141.01	<0.0001
	6 weeks	80.00	8.58	76.24	156.24	<0.0001
	3 months	83.25	8.78	79.40	162.65	<0.0001
	6 months	83.75	6.46	80.92	164.67	<0.0001

Table 3: Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH) in both groups (n=40)

PRP/ CS	Treatment	Mean	SD	95% CI		P Value
				Lower bound ($\alpha=2.5\%$)	Upper bound ($\alpha=97.5\%$)	
PRP	Before treatment	68.50	4.07	66.72	70.28	
	2 weeks	63.5	3.89	56.10	61.90	<0.0001
	6 weeks	48.80	6.02	46.16	51.44	<0.0001
	3 months	38.10	6.38	35.30	40.90	<0.0001
	6 months	21.15	8.63	27.54	32.56	<0.0001
CS	Before treatment	67.95	3.49	66.42	134.37	
	2 weeks	58.40	6.35	55.62	114.02	<0.0001
	6 weeks	48.80	6.61	45.90	94.70	<0.0001
	3 months	36.65	6.68	33.72	70.37	<0.0001
	6 months	27.55	7.91	24.08	51.63	<0.0001

Table 4: Comparison of both groups (n=40)

Scale	Treatment	PRP		CS		P value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Pain VAS	Before treatment	8.30	1.42	7.90	1.48	0.3888
	2 weeks	7.2	1.2	6.05	1.05	0.0026*
	6 weeks	4.20	1.28	5.25	1.21	0.0112
	3 months	3.15	1.42	3.60	1.60	0.3539
	6 months	1.65	0.49	2.25	1.16	0.0402*
MEPS	Before treatment	51.25	12.76	55.25	11.18	0.2983
	2 weeks	61.5	11.37	72.50	9.10	0.0017*
	6 weeks	81.50	8.90	80.00	8.58	0.5906
	3 months	78.00	6.57	83.25	8.78	0.0387
	6 months	90.5	4.56	83.75	6.46	0.0005*
DASH	Before treatment	68.50	4.07	67.95	3.49	0.6490
	2 weeks	63.5	3.89	58.40	6.35	0.0040*
	6 weeks	48.80	6.02	48.80	6.61	1.0000
	3 months	38.10	6.38	36.65	6.68	0.4871
	6 months	21.15	8.63	27.55	7.91	0.0192*

Figure 1: Comparison of Pain VAS in both groups

Figure 2: Comparison of Mayo Elbow Performance Score (MEPS) in both groups

Figure 3: Comparison of Disabilities of Arm, Shoulder and Hand scale (DASH) in both groups

Figure 4: PRP injection on the lateral epicondyle

Discussion

Lateral elbow tendinopathy is predominantly a condition characterized by degeneration within the extensor carpi radialis brevis tendon, instead of an inflammatory process. Tendinopathy is a diagnosis made based on clinical observations, while tendinitis as well as tendinosis should be specifically used to describe the diagnosis based on histological findings [10].

A variety of procedures have been attempted for the management of elbow tendinopathy, including conservative approaches such as the RICE regimen, Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), manipulated therapy, pulsed ultrasound, physical activity as well as braces. These are accompanied by injection therapies such as steroids, autologous blood, platelet-rich plasma, hyaluronic acid (HA), botulinum toxins, and dry needle therapy. If these treatments are unsuccessful, surgical release for the lateral epicondylar tendons may be considered [11].

The present study aimed at contrasting the outcomes of autologous platelet-rich plasma injection therapy versus steroid therapy. A prior study shown a significant reduction in pain by the use of steroid injections in the short term for lateral elbow tendinopathy [12]. However, other studies have suggested that the observed outcomes may be attributed to the placebo effect caused by the injection or the natural resolution of a self-limiting condition [13].

PRP has shown significant efficacy in promoting tissue repair in persistent injuries, tendinitis, as well as bone regeneration. One potential reason for the enduring impact of PRP in chronic tendinopathy is its ability to stimulate revascularization and improve healing at the cellular level [14]. A separate trial demonstrated significant pain reduction in 28 patients with tennis elbow following the administration of autologous blood injections. In a study conducted by Varshney et al., 83 patients were divided into two groups: one group of 50 patients treated with corticosteroids and another group of 33 patients treated with PRP. The results showed that six months after treatment with PRP, those suffering from elbow epicondylitis experienced significant reductions in their VAS ($P < 0.05$) and MAYO ($P < 0.05$) scores compared to those treated with steroids. However, no statistical difference was observed between the two groups at 1 and 2 months after the intervention. According to a study, individuals who received PRP treatment showed a significant improvement in grip strength after 3 months [15].

In relation to the pathology of tennis elbow, a study revealed the presence of a "Mesenchymal syndrome" that increases the likelihood of tendinosis and aberrant blood vessels at various locations. This consistent degenerative pattern is supported by histological research. It is now widely acknowledged that there is an absence of inflammatory cells and a notable presence of degenerative elements [16].

There is strong evidence at level 1 indicating that corticosteroid injections provide only short-term benefits, with no long-term advantages and the potential for harm over extended periods. This has prompted demands for a decrease or cessation of their utilization [17].

Moreover, the choice of which place to administer the injection is a subject of debate and lacks a definitive solution. Two areas with reduced blood supply have been recognized: one near the lateral epicondyle & another 2-3 cm below the extensor origin. The significance of these areas in regard to the effectiveness of injections is uncertain. There is a significant differential between injections administered directly into the tendon and those administered outside the tendon. However, there are currently no guidelines available about the criteria for selecting patients for each therapy [18].

Our study aligns with the findings that both groups experienced substantial improvements during the follow-up period. However, the corticosteroid group had a few recurrences, whereas the PRP group had no recurrences until six months. Additionally, the PRP group showed greater long-term clinical improvement compared to the corticosteroid group in view of pain, AODL, return to sports. Our research, which did not provide any local anaesthetic during injection, found that the corticosteroid group exhibited early improvement contrasted to the PRP group. The primary limitations of our study are the limited sample size and insufficient duration of follow-up. Additional research with a larger sample size and longer follow-up period is necessary.

Conclusion

In our study, the findings of the two groups over the follow-up period indicate that steroid injection provides early pain relief and improved function relative to the PRP group at the 2-week follow-up. However, both groups exhibit similar results at the 6-week and 3-month follow-ups. However, the outcomes of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) treatment show significant improvement during the 6-month follow-up period. Therefore, the PRP demonstrates superior outcomes during the 6-month follow-up period.

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